

COLORIMETRIC DETECTION OF METAL IONS WITH TWEEN COATED GOLD NANOPARTICLE

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Keywords: *metal ions, gold nanoparticle, tween, colorimetric sensor*

1. Introduction

Nanomaterial with unique physico-chemical properties causes potential to be applied in many new and exciting fields [1]. Particularly, due to their high optical and electrical stabilities, nanoparticles (NPs) are courting application in many fields, such as catalysis, nano/biosensor, surface enhanced Raman spectroscopy (SERS), electronics and medicine [2-6].

The localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) is one of the optical-properties of NPs. When metallic NP is irradiated by light, the oscillating electric field causes the conduction electrons to oscillate coherently [7]. The oscillating LSPR phenomena could be used as sensor system [8]. Especially, it has been being studied colorimetric sensor using LSPR variation of NPs, which was induced by switching of aggregation or dispersion state in specific condition, such as being target material, pH and temperature [9]. Functionalized NPs will be aggregated or dispersed when the target material exists around NPs. Thus, the NPs in specific condition cause the variation of LSPR, and then induce the color change of NPs colloidal solution. Colorimetric variation of the colloidal solution can be easily confirmed the target material without additional analyzing equipment [10].

In this study, we synthesized tween coated AuNPs, referred to as tween-AuNPs, and tried to confirm the applicability as metal ion detector. Tween have been used in pharmaceuticals, cosmetics and food preparation [11-13], and also used for stabilizer of NPs because it is acted as surfactant having hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups. When metal ion is contacted or bound with tween-AuNPs, which make complex with metal ion and caused aggregation of tween-NPs [14-16]. Using this process with controlling surround conditions, tween-AuNPs can be used metal ion detection.

2. Experiment

2.1. Preparation of tween-AuNPs

Tween-AuNPs colloid was prepared by dissolving 1 M tween20 (Sigma-Aldrich) and 0.25 mM HAuCl₄ (Kojima) in DI water. And then, 0.1 mL of 0.1 M ascorbic acid (Sigma-Aldrich) was added to this mixed solution. The color of solution was changed from colorless to red. Finally, prepared tween-AuNPs was washed several times by DI water and re-dispersed into DI water with few NaOH (Sigma-Aldrich).

2.3. Detection of metal ion by tween-AuNPs

Selective aggregation of tween-AuNPs was observed by 1 mg/L of Fe²⁺, Co²⁺, Ni²⁺, Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Pd²⁺, Cd²⁺, Pb²⁺, Hg²⁺, Ag⁺, Au³⁺ and As³⁺ (all of Sigma-Aldrich). The color changes were detected with naked eye and UV-vis spectroscopy.

2.2. Characterization of tween-AuNPs

Morphological property of tween-AuNPs was observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEM-1010, JEOL, Japan) and optical property was analyzed UV-Vis spectroscopy (UV-1800, Shimadzu, Japan).

3. Result and Discussion

Tween coated AuNPs was prepared for using colorimetric sensor. When tween is used for stabilizer in synthesis process of AuNPs, tween-NPs will be easily prepared using weak reducing agent without seed or additional heating. Tween-AuNPs prepared had spherical shape with about 50 nm and was observed uniform structure by TEM analysis (Fig.1). In the analyzing LSPR of the AuNPs by UV-Vis spectroscopy, it was observed only one absorbance peak (523 nm). At Mie's theory, spherical metallic NPs is oscillated the electric field by light, which causes the conduction electrons to oscillate coherently, and this result depends on

morphological property. LSPR variation of NPs can be expected by the field outside energy (E_{out}), following this equation (eq.1) [7]:

$$E_{out} = E_0 \hat{x} - \alpha E_0 \left[\frac{\hat{x}}{r^3} - \frac{3x}{r^5} (x\hat{x} + y\hat{y} + z\hat{z}) \right] \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha = g_d a^3 \quad (2)$$

$$g_d = \frac{\epsilon_i - \epsilon_0}{\epsilon_i + 2\epsilon_0} \quad (3)$$

Where, α is the sphere polarizability, and \hat{x} , \hat{y} and \hat{z} are the usual unit vectors. And the factor g_d plays the key role in determining the wavelength dependence and the metal dielectric constant ϵ_i is strongly dependent on wavelength. According to this equation, unique LSPR of NPs depends on polarizability of the NPs, which is being difference with morphological property. Therefore, NPs colloid shows difference color according to the condition of NPs.

Fig.1. UV-Vis spectra of tween-AuNPs. (Inset) TEM image of tween-AuNPs (Scale bar= 50 nm).

Fig.2. Scheme of tween-AuNPs aggregation by the metal ions.

Tween is well-known for typical amphoteric material (surfactant), having both hydrophilic and hydrophobic groups, and thus acts as stabilizer to maintain stability of NPs on surface of the particle. In addition, it will make complex with metal ion, when metal ions are being around the NPs, followed by inducing aggregation of each tween-AuNPs (Fig.2).

Fig.3. Image of tween-AuNPs colloids with various metal ions.

We tested the possibility of colorimetric sensor of tween-AuNPs for metal ion detecting; Fe^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , Hg^{2+} , Ag^+ , Au^{3+} and As^{3+} . Tween-AuNPs was observed selective changes from red to purple for Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cd^{2+} , as shown in Fig.3. As mentioned before, tween on the NPs form complex with metal ion. OH groups of organic material (hydrophilic part) of tween will be combined with metal ion as ion-chelating reaction, and then complex compound will be formed [14-16]. Therefore, metal ion exposed tween on AuNPs formed complex with each other, which caused aggregation of each NPs and variation of LSPR. Finally, this variation caused color changes of tween-AuNPs colloid. In this study, it was progress in basic solution due to ion strength of tween was enhanced. Selective aggregation can have been observed at Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Cd^{2+} . Thus, this result means that selective ion detection can be possible by controlling ion strength.

The morphological change of tween-AuNPs with metal ion was observed by TEM analysis (Fig.4). TEM image clearly showed selective aggregation of tween-AuNPs with specific metal ions. While tween-AuNPs had high dispersion stability in DI water, after bind with metal ions, aggregated tween-AuNPs can have been observed.

In addition, measuring absorbance by UV-Vis spectroscopy, LSPR of tween-AuNPs was analyzed with various metal ions (Fig.5). While untreated tween-AuNP had one peak (523 nm), after exposed metal ion, it was observed intensity variation of absorbance peak, which decreased at specific peak and increased at over 600 nm of absorbance values. And this LSPR variation can be analyzed selective aggregation through established study; specific peak of NPs will shift to long-wavelength when NPs is growing or aggregating [7].

Therefore, selective aggregation of tween-AuNPs with metal ion caused LSPR variation, and which caused colorimetric changes of the AuNPs colloid. As this result, tween-AuNPs has possibility for colorimetric sensor and can be applied for metal ion detector using controlling ion strength.

Fig.4. TEM image of tween-AuNPs with the metal ions (Scale bar= 50 nm)

Fig.5. UV-Vis spectra of tween-AuNP colloid with various metal ions.

Consequently, tween gave stability to AuNPs and helped to synthesizing homogeneous spherical NPs. Synthesized tween-AuNPs reacted with metal ions by ion-chelation, and it caused aggregation of the NPs. Especially, by controlling ion strength, ion-chelation can take selectively. Therefore, as this result, we confirm that tween-AuNPs can be applied to colorimetric sensor for detecting metal ion.

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